

De-icing coating fabricated via molecules' migration in high voltage insulators

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Many recent researches have been proposed on the de-icing coatings such as the super-hydrophobic coatings, electro-thermal coatings, opto-thermal coatings etc., which are keen in the security of high voltage insulators. However, many factors such as ultra-high electric field, flashover and aging of polymers could disable the performances of the coatings.

As a kind of isolative, nontoxic and relatively cheap polymer, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is keen for its applications in high voltage insulators. It is found that PDMS doped with alkyl molecules has outstanding capability in reducing ice accumulation. When temperature decreases down to the freezing point, alkyl molecules will migrate onto the surface of the coating via phase separation and reduce the surface energy, which will obviously decrease the nucleation and adhesion of water droplets. Moreover, the already accumulated ice will fall off by natural wind blowing, vibration or its weight due to the ultra low adhesion force between polymer and molecules film. Furthermore, the alkyl molecules can also migrate reversely back into the polymer under relatively higher temperature, which will help relief the loss of molecules. On the other hand, nanoparticles are also adopted in the coating to achieve slow release of alkyl molecules, which has been proved to successfully prolong the life of the de-icing coating.

Keywords: de-icing; PDMS; coating; nanoparticle; hydrophobicity;